

MODERN TEACHING METHODS USED IN TEACHING ECONOMICS AT INSTITUTE

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ABSTRACT

When organizing economics classes at institute, it is important to use active teaching methods, because they allow students to understand the practical significance of economics, apply theoretical knowledge in this discipline in practice, understand the structure and functioning mechanism of certain enterprises, etc. According to the degree of activation of students and the nature of their educational and cognitive activity, they differ: imitation methods, based on pedagogical techniques and special forms of conducting classes, in which educational, cognitive and research activities are based on imitation of future professional and practical activities, and non-imitation methods, which are based on real professional and practical situations. The purpose of the article is to study the organizational and methodological process of teaching economics at institute.

A teaching method is a way of interrelated activities between a teacher and students to achieve the goals of learning, development and education. The choice of teaching methods depends on many circumstances and conditions of the educational process, the nature and content of the educational subject, specifically on:

1. The level of knowledge and skills of the teacher. The teacher needs to know and understand the essence of the method, the classification of teaching methods, the basis of one or another type of classification, and be able to apply them in various situations and combinations. Using one or another system of methods, diverse or complementary to each other, focused on achieving a common goal, the teacher establishes feedback with students, identifies the level of acquisition of knowledge and skills, determines the effectiveness of using methods and makes adjustments, thereby increasing his level of professional competence.
2. The general goal and objectives of training, features of the subject, topic, planned goals and objectives of a particular lesson.
3. The content of educational material selected by the teacher.

4. The level of development of students, their ability to learn, capabilities and age characteristics.
5. The role of a method or a combination of methods in the development of students' cognitive activity, their activity, independence and creativity.
6. Time [1].

At the institute, in the first year, the student should be familiar with such concepts as entrepreneurship, state finances, taxes and the country's tax system, supply and demand, banks and banking, and the basics of marketing.

A combination of lectures and practical classes is necessary; the creative component of the lesson is important. The teacher should design lesson plans in such a way that new material forces the student to refer to the material already covered, i.e. so that there is a constant process of repetition, and, consequently, better assimilation of the material.

In institute, teaching economics allows you to move from basic knowledge to the formation of active mental activity, learning to analyze and critically evaluate situations, factual data, economic decisions, i.e. active forms of application of acquired knowledge. The types of lessons and the use of various forms of teaching economics to students will be discussed below.

Thus, the student, upon graduating from institute, will have an idea of the basics of economics, the most important terms and concepts, scientists who have influenced the current state of the economy. Also, the student must understand the relationship of economics with other branches of knowledge, understand its importance and significance.

Methods used in economics lessons can be divided into the following groups [2]:

- Methods of one-way presentation of educational material (teaching): story, explanation, lecture.
- Methods of two-way presentation of material: dialogue, debate, discussion, brainstorming, group work, business games;
- Methods of illuminating empirical experience (exchange of information, experience, etc.);
- Methods of various types of training: problem-based, heuristic, student-oriented, etc.;
- Methods of control and feedback (conversation, consultation, testing, test, exam, etc.).

As part of an institute course in economics, it is advisable to use this type of active learning as business games. They contribute to the formation of not only professional, but also job-related knowledge, skills and abilities. A business game is a model replacement of two realities - production processes and processes of human activity in it.

Methodological support for the business game should include N.P. Drozdova, E.G. Efimova, M.F. Kolesnikova. Active teaching methods: Educational and methodological manual [3]:

- 1) initial information about the business game;
- 2) methodology for preparing and conducting a business game;
- 3) a set of various forms and other documentation.

The use of various teaching methods and their combination makes it possible to achieve the best results in teaching economics to students, obtaining comprehensive knowledge of the subject, developing creative thinking, and the ability to set problems and solve them.

Textbook for students of pedagogical institutes and pedagogical colleges is a systematically used form of organizing the activities of a permanent staff of teachers and

students in a certain period of time to solve the problems of teaching, educating and developing students.

Currently, there are several criteria by which it is possible to classify the types of lessons Azimov L.B. Economics lessons at institute. Depending on the various psychological and pedagogical stages of students mastering the material [6]:

- Lessons on learning new material;
- Lessons to consolidate knowledge, skills and abilities;
- Repetitive and generalizing lessons;
- Lesson of control, assessment and correction of students' knowledge;
- Combined lessons.

2. Depending on the teaching methods used in the lesson:

- Lessons - lectures;
- Lessons - seminars;
- Lessons – workshops [4].

When studying this training course, it is necessary to take into account these features and organize different types of lessons differently. A lesson in learning new material can take place in various forms: lectures, workshops, or games. The purpose of this type of lesson is to study and primary awareness of new educational material by students, to comprehend the connections and relationships in the objects of study.

The main time is devoted to the transfer and assimilation of new knowledge, skills and abilities. During the lesson, various methods are used to enhance student activity: giving the material presented a problematic nature, including various examples in the material being studied, including real examples from the surrounding reality, involving students in an active discussion of the questions posed by the teacher. The teacher activates the attention and mental activity of students, systematizes the knowledge they have acquired [5].

Lesson structure for learning new economics material:

1. Organizational beginning, introduction to the lesson (preparation for mastering new material, linking concepts already covered in previous lessons with new material);
2. Setting goals and objectives for the lesson;
3. Presentation and explanation of new material, including both the teacher's explanation and students' independent familiarization with the material (involving students in a conversation about the problems under consideration, working with reference books, etc.);
4. Students carry out practical work to consolidate new material (setting tasks for work in small groups, discussing examples given by the teacher, using active and game teaching methods);
5. Voice over homework and comments on it;
6. Summing up the lesson, answering students' questions on the topic of the lesson [6].

In conclusion, practical classes should be organized in such a way that students constantly feel the increasing complexity of the tasks being performed, experience positive emotions from experiencing their own success in learning, and are engaged in intense creative work and searching for correct and accurate solutions. An individual approach and productive pedagogical communication are of great importance. When developing assignments and lesson plans, the teacher must take into account the level of preparation and interest of each student,

acting as a consultant. Conducting lessons and workshops allows students to better understand theoretical issues and understand the practical significance of economics in the modern world. Practical classes are designed to deepen, expand, and detail the knowledge acquired during lecture classes in a generalized form, as well as to promote the development of professional skills. They develop scientific thinking and speech, allow students to test their knowledge and act as a means of prompt feedback.

References:

1. Educational standard of secondary (complete) general education in social science (including economics and law).
2. Educational standard of secondary (complete) general education in social studies. Profile level.
3. Azimov L.B. Economics lessons. M.: Aspect - Press, 2015 - p.71.
4. Drozdova N.P., Efimova E.G., Kolesnikova M.F. Active teaching methods: Educational and methodological manual / Under the general editorship. F.-Y. Kaiser, G.G. Bogomazova, Z.A. Sabova. - St. Petersburg, 2022. - p.296.
5. Ivanov S.I. Teaching the course "Fundamentals of Economic Theory": a manual for teachers of grades 10-11 in general education institutions. Profile level of education. St. Petersburg: Vita-Press, 2005 - p.320.
6. Kaiser F.J. Methods of teaching economic disciplines. Book for teachers. St. Petersburg: Vita-Press, 2007 - p.184.